

SEARCH FOR NEW INSECTICIDES. PART II

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Several alkyl- and halogen-substituted phenolic esters of chloroacetic acid and the corresponding *o*-hydroxyketones, obtained on rearrangement, and 2-allyloxy-4:5-dimethyl- α -furophenone have been prepared with a view to studying their insecticidal activity.

The derivatives of chloroacetic acid are known to be potent insecticides. Hence, we prepared six chloroacetates of different phenols by the action of chloroacetyl chloride on the appropriate phenols, following the method of Spasov (*Ann. Univ. Sofia*, 1938-39, 2, 35, 289). Most of the phenols taken were halogen-substituted as Dormal, Delvaux and Dills (*J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1950, 43, 915) found that the chlorination of phenol derivatives increased the insecticidal efficiency.

Martin and Wain (*Nature*, 1944, 154, 514) have suggested that the liberation of hydrochloric acid is the cause of the insecticidal efficiency of D. D. T. Chloroacetophenone readily produces hydrogen chloride (Fieser and Fieser, "Organic Chemistry", 2nd Ed., p. 686); thus the chloroacetyl group may act as powerful poisonous component for insects. Keeping this in view, we have prepared six *o*-hydroxyketones by the Fries rearrangement of the above esters at 110° without solvent. Because of their *o*-hydroxyketonic nature, the phenolic groups of these compounds are in the chelated form, and hence, their lipid solubility should be more than that of the corresponding parent phenol. The ketonic group itself being lipophilic in nature adds to the lipid solubility. As the phenols themselves are toxic compounds, these compounds containing additional toxophore and having more lipid solubility should be better contact insecticides (Laugger, Martin and Muller, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 918).

Gilman *et. al.* (*Iowa State College J. Sci.*, 1932, 6, 439; 1933, 7, 419) have shown that α -furoates are good insecticides. Hence, considering that α -furoyl group may be an insect poisonous component, we prepared 2-allyloxy-4:5-dimethyl- α -furophenone by the etherification (Chen and Somerford, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4694) of 2- α -furoyl-3:4-dimethylphenol, described earlier (Tiwari and Tripathi, *this Journal*, 1954, 31, 841). This compound possesses allyl group as toxophore, ether linkage and ketonic group having lipophilic properties (Chen *et. al.*, *loc. cit.*) and α -furoyl group as an additional insect poisonous component. Thus, it may be a potent insecticide. The work on their insecticidal activity is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Esters of Chloroacetic Acid.—The esters of chloroacetic acid prepared are summarised in Table II.

TABLE I

o-Hydroxy-*o*-chloroacetophenones and their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

Ester.	Hydroxyketone.	B. P.	%Yield.	%Carbon.	2,4-Ditrophenylhydrazone.		M. P.	Mol. formula.	%Nitrogen.		
					%Hydrogen.	%Nitrogen.					
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.		
2-Bromo-P	3-Bromo-A	174°/40 mm.	40.0	38.45	38.50	2.92	2.40	207°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₂ ClBr	13.41	12.04
3-Ethyl-P	4-Ethyl-A	166°/37	76.0	60.12	60.45	5.04	5.54	194°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	15.22	14.74
4-Bromo-P	5-Bromo-A	164°/35	80.0	38.43	38.50	2.79	2.40	215°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₂ ClBr	13.44	13.04
2,4-Dichloro-P	3,5-Dichloro-A	128° (m.p.)	82.0	40.47	40.09	1.84	2.09	192°	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	13.69	13.35
2-Chloro- <i>tert</i> .-butyl-P	3-Chloro-5- <i>tert</i> .-butyl-A	180°/41	86.0	54.61	55.18	5.77	5.36	195°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	12.48	13.70
3,4,4-Dimethyl-P	4,5-Dimethyl-A	164°/38	86.0	60.19	60.45	5.84	5.34	210°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	14.69	14.79

[P = phenyl chloroacetate; A = 2-hydroxy-*o*-chloroacetophenone].

TABLE II.

No.	Esters.	B. P.	% Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	2-Bromo-P*	135°/11 mm.	58.0	C ₈ H ₈ O ₂ ClBr	38.80	38.50	2.82	2.40
2	3-Ethyl-P	128°/10	88.0	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂ Cl	60.13	60.45	5.97	5.54
3	4-Bromo-P	139°/11, 36°(m.p.)	76.0	C ₈ H ₈ O ₂ ClBr	38.22	38.50	2.76	2.40
4	2:4-Dichloro-P	143°/12	73.0	C ₈ H ₅ O ₂ Cl ₂	39.57	40.09	2.51	2.09
5	2-Chloro-4- <i>tert.</i> -butyl-P	142°/11	74.0	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	54.77	55.18	5.07	5.36
6	3:5-Dimethyl-P	135°/12	82.0	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂ Cl	60.93	60.45	5.27	5.54

P = phenyl chloroacetate.

Fries Rearrangement of the Esters.—The ester (1.0 M) was rearranged by 1.1 M anhydrous aluminium chloride, and the *o*-hydroxyketone was isolated by following the usual method (Tiwari and Tewari, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 79). The content left after distillation of the *o*-hydroxyketone in the first two cases was worked up for the *para*-isomer, which was found to be absent. The *o*-hydroxyketones, so obtained, gave violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and afforded crystalline red precipitate with dilute caustic soda, thus conforming to Pymar's tests of the *o*-hydroxyketones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280). These *o*-hydroxyketones and their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones are summarised in Table I.

2-Allyloxy-4:5-dimethyl- α -furophenone.—A mixture of 2-hydroxy-4:5-dimethyl- α -furophenone (3.0 g.), allyl bromide (2.0 g.), freshly fused potassium carbonate (4.0 g.) and acetone (50.0 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 10 hours. Soon after the refluxing started a heavy precipitate of potassium bromide began to separate. After the period the contents were cooled, mixed with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed successively with 5% caustic soda solution and water and finally dehydrated over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ether was removed by distillation and the residual oil distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. 163°/22 mm., yield 2.4 g. (Found: C, 75.48; H, 6.64. C₁₆H₁₆O₂ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.25 per cent).

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